

A Colorimetric Test for Compounds Containing CH, CH₂ and CH₃ Contiguous to Negative Groups : A Note.

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In some experiments for the detection of oil soluble proteins, acetone solution of the fat was tested with an alkaline solution of picric acid ; an instantaneous red coloration was produced. Blank experiment showed that the coloration was due to acetone. The test was then extended to other ketones and then to aldehydes. It was found that all aldehydes and ketones having contiguous CH, CH₂ or CH₃ groupings gave similar red coloration whereas other aldehydes and ketones like formaldehyde, benzaldehyde and benzophenone in which the above groupings are absent, did not produce any colour. Similar observations have been previously made by Bitto (*Annalen*, 1892, 269, 377, 1892, 267, 372) who found that *m*-dinitrobenzene, *m*-dinitrotoluene, *m*-dinitronaphthalene and sodium nitroprusside in alkaline media produce red to violet colour with aldehydes and ketones having CH₂ or CH₃ contiguous to CHO or CO groups.

In searching for the reason for such coloration it was thought that the latter was due to the activity of CH, CH₂ and CH₃ being in proximity to the negative groups CHO and CO. The correctness of this view would naturally lead to the production of colour with other compounds containing those active units attached to other negative groups like NO₂, CN, CO₂Et etc. This has been found to be the case as nitromethane, malonic ester, cyanoacetic ester, etc., give red colour with alkaline picric acid solution. All varieties of compounds have been examined and the test has been found to respond very satisfactorily. Generally it has been found that the production of colour always happens when the contiguous negative groups contain oxygen atom and is particularly associated with compounds containing CH₂ or CH₃ responding to Claisen's condensation reaction.

For the purpose of the colorimetric test a 0.05% alcoholic solution of picric acid (1 c.c.) was taken to which approximately 2*N*-caustic soda solution (2 drops) was added and to the faintly yellow solution, thus produced, a slight quantity of the substance to be tested was added. In the case of insoluble substance a little more alcohol was used. Table I gives the results obtained by the reagent whilst some of the results with Bitto's reagents are shown for comparison in Table II. It may be seen that while picric acid reaction is general Bitto's reagents fail in many cases.

TABLE I.

Reagent used—alkaline soln. of picric acid (faint yellow colour).

Compounds tested.	Colour produced.	Ionone (α)	Red
Formaldehyde	No change.	Nonyl aldehyde	"
Benzaldehyde	"	<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzoyl acetophenone	Orange-yellow
Benzophenone	"	<i>p</i> -Tolylbenzoylmethane	Brown
Benzil	"	Nitromethane	Red
Benzoin	"	Malonic ester	"
Acetaldehyde	Red	Cyanoacetic ester	"
Phenylacetaldehyde	"	Oxaloacetic ester	"
Acetone	"	Acetoacetic ester	"
Acetophenone	"	*2-Methyl-3-ethyl-1 : 4- β -naphthapyrone	"
Acrolein	"	*7-Nitro-2-methyl-3- <i>isopropyl</i> chromone	"
Cinnamic aldehyde	"	*6-Bromo-2-methyl-3-propylchromone	"
Citral	Brown	*6-Chloro-2 : 3-dimethylchromone	"
Benzylacetone	Red	*7-Nitro-2-methyl-3-propylchromone	"
<i>cyclo</i> Hexanone	"	*8-Chloro-2-methyl-3-propylchromone	"
<i>o</i> -Methylcyclohexanone	"		
<i>m</i> -Methylcyclohexanone	"		
<i>p</i> -Methylcyclohexanone	"		

* These compounds have been shown to have active CH₃ group (Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 28, 31, 389.)

TABLE II.

Compounds..	With <i>m</i> -dinitro- benzene.	With 3 :5-dinitro- toluene.	With sodium nitro- prusside.
Formaldehyde	No change	Violet	No change
Acetaldehyde	„	No change	Pink
Phenylacetaldehyde	Violet	Pink	No change
Acetone	„	Violet	Pink
Acetophenone	„	„	„
Benzophenone	No change	No change	No change
Citral	Violet	Violet	Pink
<i>cyclo</i> Hexanone	„	„	„
Nitromethane	„	Pink	Green
Malonic ester	„	„	Pink
Acetoacetic ester	No change	No change	„
Cyanoacetic ester	Violet	„	„

m-Dinitronaphthalene could not be tested as its alkaline solution is itself red.

In conclusion we wish to express our sincerest thanks to Dr. P. B. Sarkar for the active interest he has taken during the progress of the work.

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Received May 2, 1934.

